

Dynamic Crush of Hollow Glass Microsphere Reinforced Polyurethane Matrix Composites

Dr. Colleen M. Murray
Dr. Norman M. Wereley

Department of Aerospace Engineering
University of Maryland, College Park

A. JAMES CLARK
SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING

Crashworthiness

The ability of a system to protect its occupants in case of impact

Crashworthiness: Seating Systems

Protects during hard landing

Uses vertical stroke to absorb energy

**Designed for 14.5 g on the lumbar load
(2,064 lbs) of a 50% male (171 lbs)**

Crashworthiness: Bulkhead Injuries

Protects during bulkhead impact

**Designed to meet the head injury
criteria (HIC)**

**HIC identifies the likelihood of
head injury based on an impact**

Cellular Materials

Typical Energy Absorber

Typical Cellular Material

Current HGM Reinforced Composites

Types of HGM Reinforced Composites

Metal Matrices

- Aluminum
- Titanium
- Iron
- Magnesium
- Zinc
- Copper
- Continuous Fibers
- Graphite
- Superalloys

Polymer Matrices

Thermosetting

- Epoxy resin
- Phenolic resin
- Cyanate esters
- Polyamides
- Polyurethanes
- Unsaturated polyester

Thermoplastic

- Polyethylene
- Polypropylene
- Polystyrene
- Nylon

Ceramic Matrices

- Carbon
- Zirconia
- Silicon Carbide
- Silicon Nitride
- Zirconia Carbide

Hybrid Matrices

Biosynthesized

Nano synthesized

Frequently referred to as syntactic foam since it uses a hard matrix

Current HGM Reinforced Composites

Elastomeric matrices have a particulate introduced (HGMs), therefore composite is a more appropriate term

Manufacturing of HGM EMC

K46 Microspheres, 3M
0.46 g/cc, $\phi = 40 \mu\text{m}$

Freeman 1035 Polyurethane
Elastomer

Hand mix and pull vacuum

HGM EMC Imaging

40% v_f

65% v_f

SEM of 60% v_f

Experimental Testing

Nomenclature

Peak stress is maximum stress during the elastic region

Plateau stress is the average stress during plastic region

Goal: Equilibrate peak and plateau stresses

Quasi-Static Testing

Sphere Interactions

Quasi-Static Testing

Experimental Testing

Introduction to Dynamic Testing

Data Outputs

Determining Force and Displacement

$$\dot{z} = \int_0^t \ddot{z}(t) dt$$

$$z = \int_0^t \dot{z}(t) dt$$

$$z(0) = 0$$

$$\dot{z}(0) = -V_0$$

$$F = m\ddot{z}$$

Relationship between Crush and Velocity

Calculating Energy Absorbed

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$$
$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta z}{z}$$

Calculating Energy Absorbed

Dynamic Characterization of 60% v_f

Crush Efficiency of 60% v_f

Energy Absorbed Efficiency of 60% v_f

Crush Efficiency: Effect of V_f and V_0

As v_f increases, the η_c becomes more linear across the stroke
As V_0 increases, maximum η_c increases

Energy Absorbed Efficiency: Effect of V_f and V_0

As v_f increases, strain at densification increases until a maximum v_f is achieved
 As V_0 increases, maximum η_{EA} increases until a maximum V_0 is reached

Conclusions

- As a compressive load is applied to the composite, the stress increases, bringing the HGMs in contact
- Quasi-static testing provides a lower bound prediction of the crush and energy absorption efficiency for the dynamic test conditions
- Under dynamic crush for HGM vol% from 60-70%, there appears to be a maximum value of peak crush efficiency for the 65% sample
- Under dynamic crush for HGM vol% from 60-70%, the peak energy absorbed efficiency increases monotonically as vol% increases

Questions?

Article

Energy Absorption Behavior of Elastomeric Matrix Composites Reinforced with Hollow Glass Microspheres

Gabrielle Schumacher, Colleen M. Murray

Composites Research Laboratory, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Maryland, College Park, MD 20742, USA; gabischu01@gmail.com (G.S.); cmmurray@umd.edu (C.M.M.); pj@umd.edu (J.P.); * Correspondence: wereley@umd.edu

Abstract: Hollow glass microsphere (HGM) reinforced composites are a suitable alternative to energy absorption materials in the automotive and aerospace industries, because of their high crush efficiency and energy absorption characteristics. In this study, a polyurethane elastomeric matrix was reinforced with HGMs for HGM loadings ranging from 0 to 70 vol% (volume fraction). Quasi-static uniaxial compression tests were performed, subjecting the composite to compressive strains of up to 65%, to assess stress vs. strain and energy absorption characteristics. The results reveal that samples with a higher concentration of spheres generally exhibit better crush efficiency. Specifically, the highest crush efficiency was observed in samples with a 70 vol% HGM loading. A similar relationship was reflected in the energy absorption efficiency results, with the highest energy absorption observed in the 65 vol% sample. A correlation exists between the concentration of HGMs and important metrics such as mean crush stress and energy absorption efficiency. However, it is crucial to note that the optimal choice of sphere concentration varies depending on the desired performance characteristics of the material.